

Metallotolerance of soil bacteria *Streptomyces lusitanus* found in vermicompost

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Abstract

Vermicompost is a commonly used compost soil to improve soil quality and provide fertilization for plants in agriculture because of its abundance of nutrition and diverse population of fungi and bacteria. This paper attempts to isolate bacteria from vermicompost obtained from a vermicompost box. A soil water extract-based medium and a selective medium added with Cadmium were used to perform bacteria inoculation. One bacterium was successfully isolated and purified. The purified bacterium was subjected to 16s rDNA PCR amplification and then DNA sequencing. The bacteria isolate was found to be *Streptomyces lusitanus*. A genus of *Streptomyces* is shown to have strong identification capabilities.

1. Introduction

Vermicompost is a kind of nutritious soil produced through the decomposition of worms and other decomposers of mostly kitchen waste and other organic materials [1]. Meanwhile, common compost soil relies only on bacteria and fungi to break down organic matter [2]. Both vermicompost and common composts are extremely high in bacterial concentration in comparison with normal soils. Vermicompost has been a very popular environmentally friendly fertilizer among farmers and gardeners over the recent century [2] because of its similarity to naturally fertile soils and that it does nearly no damage to the local soil habitat [1]. At the same time, it brings a population of bacterial and fungal decomposers with it into the soil, further improving soil health [3, 4].

In comparison to chemical fertilizer, compost soil is more effective in the long term and helps in the process of bioremediation of the soil, preventing it from becoming barren from over usage [1]. It can also act as a remediator along with earthworms before farming in barren or heavy metal-contaminated land [5]. These contaminants may have various sources, but were mostly due to industrial activities and mining [6]. At the same time, composting with earthworms and other agricultural organic byproducts has been shown to help detoxify the soil, and composting soil has

also proven to allow more vegetative growth on heavy metal contaminated land [5]. However, it was unclear, in the case of heavy metal contaminated soil, which of the bacteria and fungi found in vermicompost survive to assist this vegetative growth.

The target of this experiment was to identify soil bacteria that can survive in the presence of cadmium and compare their growth in contaminated and non-contaminated environments. A recipe using compost soil extract was also designed to provide the most realistic growing environment that the bacteria would be growing.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Collection of Samples

Soil (in the case of worm cast mixed with soil) samples were collected from (22.7, 114) Longhua district, Shenzhen. Located in Guangdong, China. Samples were inserted into sterilized 250 mL bottles and carried back to the lab. Then the samples were placed at 4°C before use.

2.2 Extraction of Bacteria in the Samples

Five grams of vermicompost soil sample were added to a 50 mL centrifuge tube, followed by sterilized water until the system reached 35 mL. The system was then left to sediment at room temperature for 3 minutes. The supernatant was then taken as the sample and placed into a 2 mL centrifuge tube; only 1 mL of supernatant was taken from each tube. The same process was repeated three times, ending with three identical 2 mL tubes of samples as a result. One of the three was directly stored at 4°C while the other two were diluted to 10x and 100x.

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Figure 1: Bacterial growth from different dilutions of basic and selective samples

2.3 Selective and Basic Culture Medium Preparation

Both basic and selective media were designed using soil extract.

The basic medium was named "soil basic medium" and the selective medium named "Cad selective medium". To prepare the "soil basic medium", the compost soil was extracted by centrifuging a mixture of 50 percent soil and 50 percent water in tubes of 50 mL at 8000 revolutions per minute (r/min) for 5 minutes after it was shaken up. The supernatant was taken and filtrated with filtration paper, thus becoming the soil extract mentioned earlier. The soil extract was added to the same volume of sterilized water along with 0.5 g/100 mL of dipotassium phosphate and 1.5 g agar powder per 100 mL of the system. For the preparation of "Cad selective medium", 1.6 mg/L of Cadmium was added to the "soil basic medium". The two separate systems for the basic and selective agar were then sterilized at 121 degrees under pressure steam for 15 minutes. After which each medium was poured into a culture dish (labeled selective or basic) and dried for at least 24 hrs under room temperature on a clean bench before use.

2.4 Spreading and Streaking

Spreading rods were used to spread each dilution of the soil samples onto the culture dish (as mentioned in section 2.3), with each dilution spread on a basic medium and a selective medium. Resulting in a total of 6 plates. Which were incubated in the incubator at a temperature of 37°C for about 72 hrs.

2.5 Bacterial Isolation from "Basic Soil Medium", "Cad Selective Soil Medium" and Purification

From the worm compost soil sample using "basic soil medium", one of the colonies was selected (a similar colony from "10x selective" and "10x basic" each were inoculated in selective and basic mediums respectively shown in Fig.

Figure 2: White colony isolated from the original plate

1, 2.

The bacteria colonies were then extracted from the samples and purified on plates of selective and basic agars.

These isolated plates were placed in a 37°C incubator for about 5 days before the second round of inoculation. However, only one type of white bacteria grew fast enough for the experiment.

2.6 DNA Extraction and Polymerase Chain Reaction

A soil genome DNA extraction kit from MP Biomedicals was used to break cell membranes.

To perform PCR of the 16S rRNA, 1 uL of each sample DNA was placed into a 2 mL Centrifuge tube along with 14 uL Taq polymerase, 7 uL water, 1 uL of 1492r primer (pos), 1 uL of 27f primer (neg). Creating a system of 25 uL, which was centrifuged for 5 seconds so the mixture was evenly mixed. The set temperatures for the PCR are as follows: 98 °C for 2.2 minutes to denature the DNA, 60 °C for 15 seconds for the Taq polymerase to attach, 72 °C for 5 minutes (elongation and final elongation). Samples were stored at 4 °C after PCR.

2.7 Electrophoresis Test

Gel electrophoresis was used to determine if DNA was successfully amplified. The gel consists of 1.2 grams of agarose powder, 80 mL of TAE buffer, and 4 µL of nucleic acid dye. The solution was dried in a gel mold to form a rectangular shape and focused for half an hour before being placed into the electrophoresis machine. Five microliters of PCR product were placed into each locus of the gel. A 120 Volt charge was conducted for 20 minutes before the results were compared to the DNA marker.

The electrophoresis test showed two successfully amplified 16s rDNA, according to Fig. 3, in which there are bands at 1500-1600 base pairs, which were identified by matching with the DNA marker of DL2000 from Biosharp Life Sciences.

Figure 3: Gel electrophoresis results, the first patch is the DNA indicator while the two after were the genetic materials of the inoculated cells after extraction and PCR

3. Results

3.1 Bacteria From Worm Compost Sample Grown on Basic and Cadmium Selective Mediums

The images (Fig. 1) showed that more variations of bacteria and fungi grew on the basic medium. While the comparatively observable biodiversity of the 10x diluted worm compost soil sample using “Cad selective soil medium” was much smaller, with a clear lack of varying colors and sizes of colonies. The selective sample was also slightly less dense in colonies. For the basic sample, there were observed colonies of orange and white fungi, as well as colonies of different shades of yellow bacteria. Thus, it may be concluded that the presence of a concentration of Cad may cause a decrease in the biodiversity of bacteria and fungi in soil. This phenomenon is observed in both 10x and 100x diluted samples, while in undiluted samples a dominant population of white colonies was noted.

3.2 Inoculated Bacteria from "Basic Soil Medium" and "Cad Selective Soil Medium"

The purified colonies were relatively small and smooth at first, showing a reflective white surface (Fig. 2). Over time,

the colonies became more convex in shape and grew an irregular, undefined edge. The growth process took roughly 3-4 workdays after inoculation.

3.3 DNA Sequencing

Once the success of PCR is confirmed by the gel electrophoresis test, as shown in Fig. 3, samples were sent to Tsingke Biotech Company for DNA Sanger sequencing. The sequence was then processed into FASTA format and blasted against the NCBI nucleotide database to identify the species. Both samples from selective and basic mediums were identified as *Streptomyces lusitanus* with 99 percent identity.

4. Discussion

The dilution caused quite a visible decrease in the population diversity of both fungi and bacteria on the medium. However, the bacteria identified *S. lusitanus* grew equally well in both mediums; thus, apparently it can be classified as heavy metal tolerant to a degree of 1.5 mg/L and may be able to serve its original medical and biochemical functions, such as but not limited to the production of Hyaluronidase.

4.1 *Streptomyces lusitanus*

Streptomyces lusitanus is a species of genus *Streptomyces*. A gram-positive aerobic bacterium is often used for the production of antibiotics [7]. In addition, *S. lusitanus* has shown to be capable of growing naturally in various environments including but not limited to deserts [8], marine sediments [9], dry mudflat sand [10] as well as heavy metal contaminated soil as shown by this experiment. Despite the lack of data to support that it may clean such soils directly of the specific metal, it has exemplified a few interesting effects on the medium it lives. *S. lusitanus* [11] has shown strong capability in the process of denitrifying and bioremediation.

4.2 Implications

Thus, it may be concluded that the bacteria *S. lusitanus* may not have such a significant effect on plain soil; however, it may be used to combat toxic blooms of unwanted or invasive generalist species and are highly immune to metal contamination, such as algae blooms or imbalanced soil nutrition. This could perhaps also explain a part of why vermicompost is so environmentally friendly in comparison with traditional fertilizers, which mostly aim to increase nitrate concentration in soils. Both of which contain rich nitrogen sources, but the simple molecular structure found in traditional fertilizers was more favorable to fast-growing generalist species, while the more complex and diverse molecules in vermicompost promote more even growth of various species, including ones that may have longer life cycles.

5. Conclusion

Heavy metal contamination does have a visible effect on the diversity in bacteria and fungi populations in vermicompost, but there are also populations of highly resistant bacteria that are capable of surviving in such conditions and may help balance soil nutrition and promote more equitable vegetative growth. One of which is *S. lusitanus* identified in this experiment, showing similar growth rates in both contaminated and non-contaminated media.

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